

PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF THE RADIATION CROSSLINKED SHAPE MEMORY EVA/HDPE

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Introduction and motivation

To date, some potential values of SMPs in application haven't been developed fully. For instance, the SMPs of space-deployable, to satisfying the requirements of actual using environmental condition, should have a good performance in adaptability including antioxidant property, vacuum gas characteristics and anti-radiation property. Radiation crosslinking, which has the advantages of controllable crosslinking degree, uniformity and purity, is one of the effective methods to obtain good space environment adaptability SMPs. In this paper, high density polyethylene (HDPE) and ethylene-vinyl acetate (EVA) were used as the raw materials to prepare a kind of good environment adaptability SMP.

Experiment

Materials and Equipment

- High density polyethylene(HDPE)
- Ethylene-vinyl acetate (EVA)
- Open mill to mix
- Vulcanizer
- ELV-8 electronic beam

Preparation

- The EVA/HDPE blends with different mass ratios were mixed in an open mill for 20min, with approximately the same mixing temperature of 150°C.
- The prepared blanks were shaped into plate specimens by hot pressing by a vulcanizer, with approximately the same pressure of 10 MPa.
- The plate specimens were crosslinked by 1 MeV electron beam.

Testing

Tensile test, DSC, TG, Shape memory behaviors

Experiment

- The maximum tensile properties was on the radiation dose of 150-200kGy.

- EVA / HDPE shape memory polymer maintain thermal stability at 300 °C and TML and CVCM are both far less than ECSS-Q-ST-70-02 standard.

Name	Total Mass Loss	Condensable Volatile Content of The Materials
Test result	TML=0.22%	CVCM=0.02%
ECSS-Q-ST-70-02	TML≤1.00%	CVCM≤0.10%

- Tension: fixed ratio is 95%, and the shape memory recovery ratio is 96%.
- bending: fixed ratio is 100%, and the shape memory recovery ratio is 94%.

Conclusion

- To obtain EVA/HDPE blends with good shape memory characteristics and mechanical properties, the content of EVA should be less than 30%, electron irradiation dose should be in the range from 150kGy to 200kGy.
- The EVA/HDPE blends prepared with 3:7 ratio and 160kGy irradiation dose shows good shape memory properties. When the tensile deformation reached 200%, the shape fixed rate was 95% and the recovery rate was 96%. As bending deformation was 180°, the shape fixed rate is 100% and the recovery rate is 95.5%.
- The EVA/HDPE blends prepared with 3:7 ratio and 160kGy irradiation dose shows excellent gassing performance, the total mass loss rate and the condensable volatile content of the materials was 0.22% and 0.02%, respectively.

Reference

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